

MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY OF COBALTOUS COMPLEXES AND THEIR CONSTITUTION

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Certain fairly stable cobaltous complexes of the penetration type have been prepared and their magnetic susceptibilities determined. The compounds studied are: diaquo-cobaltous ethylenediaminebisacetylacetonate, cobaltous ethylenediguanidinium sulphate, cobaltous biguanidinium sulphate and its hydroxide. Of these, the preparation of the first compound was previously described by Morgan and Smith. The moment value of about 2.6 Bohr, found for these complexes, which is considerably lower than that of simple cobaltous ion (5.04 Bohr), furnishes definite evidence that they are of the penetration class with planar structure for the fourfold co-ordination and that the magnetic moment of cobaltous cobalt in these complexes differs from the theoretically expected value on the basis of $d-s-p^3$ hybrid bonds. The discrepancy is attributed to the incomplete quenching of the orbital moment of the unpaired electron in the complex.

The co-ordination complexes can in general be sharply divided into two classes from their magnetic behaviour, as was pointed out by one of us as early as 1928 (Rāy, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 8, 73; *Z. anorg. u. allg. Chem.*, 1928, 174, 189). These were distinguished as Penetration (Einlagerung) and Associated (Anlagerung) complexes. In the former some of the shared electrons forming the co-ordinated bonds were supposed to enter the inner incomplete level of the central atom, while in the latter they were regarded to fill only the valency or the outermost levels. It was also suggested that in some of the associated complexes the co-ordinated addenda were held simply by electrostatic attraction. In later years Pauling (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 53, 1367, 3225), on the basis of quantum mechanics, developed a comprehensive theory of complex compounds, which satisfactorily accounts for their magnetic behaviour and molecular configuration. According to Pauling, in sixfold complexes where d^2-s-p^3 hybrid bonds are formed with d -orbitals of a lower quantum number, the molecule assumes an octahedral structure with considerable reduction of the magnetic moment of the central paramagnetic ion, except, of course, in the case of chromium where it remains unchanged. In many cases, e.g., for Co^{3+} , Fe^{3+} , Pt^{4+} , Ir^{3+} , Rh^{3+} , etc., the moment is reduced almost to zero and the molecule becomes diamagnetic. Where the bonds are of $s-p^4-d^2$ type with d -orbitals in the same quantum number as s and p orbitals, the configuration of the molecule remains octahedral, but there occurs practically no change in the magnetic moment of the central paramagnetic ion. Under these circumstances the complex ion may assume a resonating structure, with the co-ordination bonds resonating with ionic or ion-dipole bonds. For fourfold complexes with a bivalent central ion, Pauling assumes the possibility of two different space configurations, planar square or tetrahedral, with $d-s-p^2$ or $s-p^3$ bonds respectively. In the former a d -orbital of the penultimate level takes part in the bond formation. The tetrahedral configuration with all the bond orbitals in the same level ($s-p^3$) may, therefore, resonate with ionic or ion-dipole bond structure. Hence, the magnetic moment of the paramagnetic central ion remains practically unchanged in its tetrahedral complexes. In complexes with planar configuration, however, if as the result of bond formation there remains no unbalanced or unpaired electron in the molecule, the moment of the central paramagnetic ion practically vanishes and the molecule becomes diamagnetic. This is observed in the case of certain nickel complexes, characterised by red, yellow or orange colour, namely nickel dimethylglyoxime, potassium nickelocyanide, nickel biguanidines, etc.

In the case of cobalt, the bond formation for sixfold and fourfold complexes can, after Pauling, be illustrated as follows. The configuration of the simple cobaltous ion is also added for comparison.

[Arrows indicate the spin of the individual electrons in each orbital].

Almost all the cobalt complexes, that have already been examined magnetically, give practically the same moment for the central cobalt atom as that of the simple cobaltous ion. This suggests that the cobaltous complexes in general are of the associated type. Their physical and chemical properties also support this idea. As is well known, these associated cobaltous complexes are rather unstable and pass readily by oxidation into the cobaltic complexes, which are usually of the penetration type. But there are one or two cobaltous complexes, described in literature, whose colour (yellow or orange) and stability indicate that they are possibly of the penetration type, having planar configuration with $d-s-p^3$ bonds. Recently, however, we have succeeded in preparing a few fairly stable cobaltous biguanide complexes of bright yellow colour, presumably of the penetration type (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 20, 291). It was, therefore, considered of great interest to determine their magnetic susceptibility with a view to ascertaining the configuration of their molecule. For, it will be observed, from an examination of the electronic configuration given above, that planar cobaltous complexes with $d-s-p^3$ bonds, or an octahedral complex with d^3-s-p^3 bonds, having an unpaired electron in the molecule, should give a magnetic moment of 1.73 Bohr magnetons on the basis of Bose-Stoner's formula, $\mu_n = \sqrt{4S(S+1)}$, assuming that spin alone is effective. Whereas the moment of cobalt atom in its simple ion or associated complex, due to the presence of three unbalanced electrons, should, according to the above formula, give a moment of 3.87 Bohr magnetons. Actually, however, in the latter case the observed value is somewhat larger and is equal to 5.04 Bohr magnetons. This discrepancy is interpreted as a result of imperfect quenching of orbital moment due to weak l -interactions. It follows, therefore, that the magnetic moment of the cobaltous ion will be profoundly altered (a reduction of $5.04 - 1.73 = 3.31$ Bohr magnetons) by the formation of a penetration complex of planar square or octahedral type.

In what follows, the measurement of magnetic moment of these cobaltous complexes has been described and their results discussed.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Kahibaum's nickel-free cobalt chloride was used in the preparation of all the following cobaltous complexes,

Diaquo-cobaltous ethylenediaminebisacetylacetonate was prepared following the method described by Morgan and Smith (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2034); $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1 mol., 48 g.) dissolved in 20 c.c. of hot water, and ethylenediaminebisacetylacetonate (1 mol., 4.5 g.) and 8 c.c. of 5N-NaOH were mixed together. A green paste was formed. The mixture, on boiling, turned brownish yellow and a reddish orange crystalline product was obtained. This was filtered, washed with cold water and dried in air.

The result shows that the product is impure. Several samples were prepared with all possible care, but we could not get better results. The substance was always found to contain traces of brown products. It is insoluble in water, but dissolves readily in many organic solvents; from the latter, however, it could not be recrystallised as the solution began to darken immediately.

Cobaltous ethylenebiguanide sulphate $[\text{Co}(\text{C}_4\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_3)] \text{SO}_4 \cdot 2\frac{1}{2}\text{H}_2\text{O}$, *cobaltous biguanide sulphate* $[\text{Co}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_7\text{N}_3)_2] \text{SO}_4 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and *cobaltous biguanide hydroxide* $[\text{Co}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_7\text{N}_3)_2](\text{OH})_2$ were prepared as described in the previous paper (*loc. cit.*), and their purity verified by analysis.

Magnetic Measurements

Susceptibility measurements were made according to Guoy's method. An electromagnet

with its core made of Swedish soft iron and pole-pieces of the shape shown in the figure, fixed at a distance of 1.8 cm., was employed for these measurements. A current of about 6 amperes was found to be necessary for the magnetic saturation of the iron core, but as the field-strength with 5 amperes was only 6.5% lower, all measurements were made with the latter current to avoid undue heating of the coils. The current was taken from the main through an adjustable resistance and ammeter. A parallel circuit with a lamp was also arranged, which could momentarily be thrown in along with the main circuit just before the current was switched in or

out of the magnet. This served to ensure a slow rise or fall of the current at the start or break of the main circuit, and thus to avoid high surge current which might damage the insulation of the coils by sparking. During the actual period of measurement, however, this branch circuit was kept always cut off from the main. The centre of the maximum field between the pole-pieces was determined by a topographical survey with a tube containing a column of a paramagnetic substance like copper sulphate. The tube containing the specimens for measurement was always suspended between the poles in such a way that its lower end coincided with this centre. The field-strength was found to be uniform within a stretch of 7 mm. below or above this

point; the bottom of the specimen tube was, therefore, always in the region of maximum field even under oscillations during weighing. The field was found to be practically negligible at 8 cm. above this point. The specimen tubes were, therefore, always filled up to a height of at least 9 cm. A glass thread was used for their suspension from an adjustable hook at the bottom of one of the pans of a Bunge Analytical Balance A I, sensitive to 1/20th mg. The tube was provided with a glass stopper ending in a hook for suspension and tightly held in position by the ebonite cap as shown in the figure. The entire magnet was enclosed in a glass box with glass doors. The susceptibility was calculated from the following expression :

$$K = \frac{\chi_m \times m \times H_{\max}^2}{2l}$$

where K = force exerted on the substance by the field in dynes, χ_m = mass susceptibility, m = wt. of the substance in g., $H_{\max}$ = maximum field in gauss, l = height in cm. of the substance column in the tube.

Hence,
$$\chi_m = \frac{2l \times \text{change of weight in mg.}}{m \times H_{\max}^2 \times 1.019}$$

Finally, correction should be made for susceptibility of the air displaced by the substance, as weighings were made in air. For this, a knowledge of the density of the substance examined is, however, necessary. But as this correction is very small in magnitude, it can be neglected in the case of paramagnetic substances. Whenever this correction became necessary the following expression was used :

$$\chi_m = \frac{2l \times \text{change of wt. in mg.}}{m \times H_{\max}^2 \times 1.019} + \chi_v^* / d_s,$$

where d_s = density of the substance, T = the temperature of measurement (absolute) and χ_v^* = volume susceptibility of air at T . $H_{\max}$ was determined by using a number of standard substances like ferrous ammonium sulphate, chrome alum and copper sulphate, as accurate values for their mass susceptibilities are known. The use of nickel ammonium sulphate as standard, employed by some workers, was avoided, since values for its mass susceptibility, measured by different investigators, do not agree (cf. Jackson, *Phil. Trans.*, 1923, A, 224; Seres, *Ann. Physik*, 1933, 10, 20, 441; Bartlett, *Phys. Rev.*, 1932, ii, 41, 818). Since χ_m depends on the ratio l/m , substances in all cases were packed uniformly and tightly into the measurement tubes by gently ramming with a thin glass rod.

Ferrous ammonium sulphate (Scherring-Kahlbaum's *pro analysi* certified quality of the salt) was dissolved in cold water, acidified with a few drops of sulphuric acid and then precipitated by alcohol. The product was washed first with cold water, then with alcohol and finally dried in air. [Found : Fe (volumetrically), 14.23. Calc. Fe, 14.24 per cent].

Chrome alum was prepared from chemically pure potassium dichromate (Merck's *pro analysi* guaranteed reagent) and sulphuric acid (reagent-Kahlbaum) by reduction with alcohol. The product was then purified by recrystallisation from water by the addition of alcohol. The crystals were dried in air. [Found : Cr (volumetrically), 10.45. Calc. Cr, 10.42 per cent].

For *copper sulphate*, Scherring-Kahlbaum's sample of certified analytical reagent quality was used after careful recrystallisation. The crystals were dried in air. [Found : Cu (volumetrically), 25.49. Calc. Cu, 25.47 per cent].

χ_m for ferrous ammonium sulphate was calculated from Jackson's value (*Phil. Trans.*, 1924, A, 2241), $\chi_m (17.3^\circ) = 32.57 \times 10^{-6}$ and $\theta = -1^\circ$. The value for chrome alum was calculated from Haas and co-workers' value for $\mu_s = 3.85$ with $\theta = 0^\circ$ and that of copper sulphate from $\mu_s = 1.92$ with $\theta = -0.7^\circ$ by the same authors (*J. Commun. phys. Lab. Univ. Leiden*, 208c, 2rod).

The values of H_{max} obtained are shown in the following table.

Substance	Temp.	χ_m	H_{max} in gauss.
$FeSO_4 \cdot (NH_4)_2SO_4 \cdot 6H_2O$	32°	31.1×10^{-6}	10.15×10^3
" " "	35	30.8	10.08
$KCr(SO_4)_2 \cdot 12H_2O$	31	12.01	10.21
" " "	33	12.04	10.14
" " "	"	"	10.20
$CuSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$	32.5	5.84	10.21
			Mean 10.16×10^3

The mass susceptibility of the substances under investigation was calculated from the expression given above with the value of $H_{max} = 10.16 \times 10^3$ gauss, and ignoring the air correction which is obviously negligible for paramagnetic bodies.

1. *Diaquo-cobaltous ethylenediaminebisacetylacetonone* $[(H_2O)_2, Co, O_2, N_2, C_{12}, H_{18}]$.

$\chi_m = 7.91 \times 10^{-6}$. Temp. = 30° . $\chi_s = 317 \times 7.91 \times 10^{-6} = 2509 \times 10^{-6}$. Correction for diamagnetism = $+ 156.5 \times 10^{-6}$. $\chi_a = 2665.5 \times 10^{-6}$. $\mu_s(\text{corr.}) = 2.55$. A second sample gave $\chi_m = 6.926 \times 10^{-6}$. Temp. = 31° . $\chi_s = 2194 \times 10^{-6}$. Correction = $+ 156.5 \times 10^{-6}$. $\chi_a = 2350.5 \times 10^{-6}$. $\mu_s(\text{corr.}) = 2.40$.

2. *Cobaltous ethylenebiguanidinium sulphate* $[Co(C_6H_{10}N_{10})] SO_4 \cdot 2.5H_2O$.

$\chi_m = 6.81 \times 10^{-6}$. Temp. = 26° . $\chi_s = 428 \times 6.81 \times 10^{-6} = 2914 \times 10^{-6}$. Correction = $+ 190.0 \times 10^{-6}$. $\chi_a = 3104 \times 10^{-6}$. $\mu_s(\text{corr.}) = 2.74$.

3. *Cobaltous biguanidinium hydroxide* $[Co(C_5H_7N_3)_2](OH)_2$.

$\chi_m = 8.268 \times 10^{-6}$. Temp. = 30° . $\chi_s = 295 \times 8.268 \times 10^{-6} = 2439 \times 10^{-6}$. Correction = $+ 110.04 \times 10^{-6}$. $\chi_a = 2549.8 \times 10^{-6}$. $\mu_s(\text{corr.}) = 2.49$.

4. *Cobaltous biguanidinium sulphate* $[Co(C_5H_7N_3)_2] SO_4 \cdot 4H_2O$.

$\chi_m = 6.787 \times 10^{-6}$. Temp. = 30.2° . $\chi_s = 429 \times 6.787 \times 10^{-6} = 2912 \times 10^{-6}$. Correction = $+ 185.8 \times 10^{-6}$. $\chi_a = 3097.8 \times 10^{-6}$. $\mu_s(\text{corr.}) = 2.75$.

Corrections for the diamagnetism of other atoms, groups or ions in the complex cobaltous compounds together with any constitutive factors, as well as for the inherent diamagnetism of the cobaltous ion itself, were made in the molecular susceptibility in each case. The diamagnetic susceptibility for the cobaltous ion is assumed to be equal to that of zinc ion due to close agreement between their ionic radii. The values employed for Co^{++} and SO_4^{--} ions are -12.8×10^{-6} and -39.0×10^{-6} respectively (Kido, *K. Sci. Rep. Tohoku Imp. Univ.*, 1932, 21, 149). For other atoms or groups as also for any constitutive factor, corrected Pascal's values were adopted. From the corrected susceptibility of the central cobalt atom, its magnetic moment was calculated according to the equation :

$$\mu_s = 2.84 \sqrt{\chi_a \times T}$$

where χ_a = corrected atomic susceptibility for cobalt.

DISCUSSION

Though the substance No. 1 could not be obtained in a pure state, still its magnetic moment approaches closely the values found for the more or less pure compounds, Nos. 2, 3 and 4. These latter again do not give the same value, which may be due to the fact that they are not possibly magnetically pure. It may also result from a possible difference in θ -corrections for the compounds. But these have not been determined. In any case it gives an idea about the order of the moment value for a central cobalt atom in a co-ordinated cobaltous complex of the penetration type. As an average we may take it to be equal to 2.66 Bohr magnetons, which, it is believed, will not differ appreciably from the actual value of the pure compounds.

We may now compare this with the theoretical moment-value for cobalt in a cobaltous complex with $d-s-p^2$ or d^2-s-p^2 bonds on the basis of Pauling's theory. According to the latter the moment of such a complex will be due to the presence of one unpaired electron as shown in the figure, already described (*vide supra*). On the basis of Bose-Stoner's formula, the moment should be given by :

$$\mu_s = \sqrt{4S(S+1)} = 1.73.$$

On the other hand, if we assume that the orbital moments are not quenched, but free to orient independently as the spin moment, then the molecule should give, as required by the formula

$$\mu_s = \sqrt{4S(S+1) + L(L+1)},$$

a moment value of 3 Bohr magnetons, assuming that the lone electron occupies a 3-d orbital in the planar and a 4-d in the octahedral complex with L -value equal to 2. The experimental value of 2.66 Bohr magnetons seems to suggest that the L -moment is only partially quenched in these cobaltous complexes. It is of interest to recall in this connection that the moment of 5.04 Bohr for the cobalt atom in simple cobaltous ion, Co^{++} , or in its associated complexes, also does not follow Bose-Stoner's formula, but rather the one based on the free orientation of the L -moment, which requires 5.2 Bohr. In any case the profound alteration of the moment of Co^{++} from 5.04 to 2.66 Bohr in the above-discussed complexes furnishes a strong evidence that they are of the penetration type, and are all fourfold complexes with planar structure having more or less the same moment. The bright yellow colour of these cobaltous complexes resembling those of the corresponding nickel compounds strongly supports this view. It may also be pointed out in this connection that in its triple nitrites, e.g., $\text{K}_2\text{Ca}[\text{Co}(\text{NO}_2)_3]$, the central cobalt atom shows a magnetic moment of about 1.73 Bohr magnetons as required by Pauling's theory (Ray and Sahu, private communication; also Pauling "The Nature of the Chemical Bond", 1940, p. 116). This indicates that in these anionic octahedral complexes the orbital moment of the central cobalt atom is completely quenched as might be expected from their electronic configuration in which the unbalanced electron, responsible for magnetic moment, is raised to the outermost λ -d level, where it is fully exposed to the influence of the field of the neighbouring atoms and ions (*vide figure above*). The configuration of the fourfold planar cobaltous complexes, on the other hand, shows that the unbalanced electron in their case lies much deeper in the 3-d level and is thereby protected from the field of the surrounding atoms or ions, making the L -moment free to orient in the magnetic field. The effect might also be dependent upon the strength of the spin-orbit coupling, as well as upon that of the electric field of the neighbouring atoms or ions, which varies with their nature and their distance.

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